

STRUCTURAL AND THERMAL ANALYSIS OF FINNED SURFACE OF AN IC ENGINE USING FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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Abstract

In the thermal analysis of engine cylinders, fins are strategically placed on the cylinder surface to enhance heat transfer through convection. Understanding the dissipation of heat from the engine cylinder via fins, as well as the stresses induced by temperature and pressure, is crucial for effective design and performance optimization. Previous literature surveys have indicated that Finite Element Method (FEM) analyses have been employed to study stresses and strains in engine components under individual conditions of pressure or temperature. However, in practical scenarios, engine chambers experience simultaneous temperature and pressure conditions. Therefore, it becomes imperative to investigate the deformations and stresses in the engine due to these combined effects to gain a comprehensive understanding and enable effective engine design, especially when integrating finned surfaces. This project considers several materials commonly used for engine blocks and extended surfaces, including aluminum 6061 alloy, titanium alloy, magnesium alloy, and gray cast iron. The components are designed using CATIA V5 software, and analysis is conducted using ANSYS Workbench. The maximum operational conditions applied include an engine temperature of 600°C and a pressure of 2.068 MPa. Through FEM analysis, it has been determined that aluminum 6061 alloy demonstrates favorable results in both structural integrity and thermal heat dissipation when compared to the other materials studied. This finding underscores the material's suitability for withstanding the combined effects of high temperature and pressure within the engine chamber while effectively managing heat transfer through the finned surfaces. By leveraging these analytical tools and insights, engineers can make informed decisions regarding material selection and design optimization, ultimately contributing to the efficiency, reliability, and performance of engine systems in various operational conditions.

Keywords: I.C Engine, FEM, Structural and thermal analysis, Materials, Fins.

1. Introduction

In an internal combustion (IC) engine, combustion occurs inside the cylinder where the chemical energy of fuel converts into mechanical energy. However, only a fraction of the total thermal energy generated—approximately 25 to 35 percent—is converted into useful work, with the remainder being rejected into the

surroundings. The high temperatures generated, reaching up to 600°C, can potentially lead to the burning of the oil film between moving parts, resulting in engine seizing. Therefore, it is critical to maintain these temperatures within safe limits. The objective of this study is to investigate the heat dissipation capabilities of fins and cylinders made from different materials. Analyzing the heat transfer rates of fins is essential to understand how effectively heat can be dissipated. Structural and thermal analyses will provide insights into the heat dissipation characteristics of the engine's surface and the stresses induced in the cylinder due to bot Pressure and temperature fluctuations. Efficient engine operation relies on effectively transferring excess heat to the atmosphere. This requires a detailed examination of the surface characteristics of various materials, including extended surfaces such as fins. Finite Element Method (FEM) analysis offers an approximate method to study thermal and structural stress distributions, as well as heat flux distributions, providing a clearer understanding of IC engine behavior.

The choice of material is crucial, particularly in terms of thermal conductivity, which plays a significant role in transferring heat from internal surfaces to external ones. Opting for materials with higher thermal conductivity can enhance heat dissipation but may also increase thermal deformation and stress levels, impacting overall engine design. Therefore, material selection should aim to minimize thermal stresses while maximizing heat flux distribution, all within cost-effective parameters. In summary, this study aims to optimize engine performance by evaluating the thermal characteristics of different materials and their ability to dissipate heat efficiently. By leveraging FEM analysis and considering material properties judiciously, engineers can enhance the reliability and longevity of IC engines under varying operating conditions.

Fins serve as crucial components in heat transfer applications, particularly in devices like heat sinks and radiators. In the realm of heat transfer studies, fins are surfaces designed to enhance the rate of heat exchange with the environment by improving convection. This enhancement is achieved by increasing the temperature gradient between the object and its surroundings, elevating the convection heat transfer coefficient, or expanding the surface area of the object. Integrating fins onto an object effectively increases its surface area, presenting an economical solution to manage heat transfer challenges. Commonly found in heat exchanging equipment such as car radiators and power plant heat exchangers, fins are also utilized in advanced technologies like hydrogen fuel cells. Nature also showcases the utility of fins, seen in adaptations like the ears of rabbits and fennec foxes, which act as natural fins to dissipate heat from circulating blood.

The primary role and significance of fins in heat exchangers are to efficiently transfer heat away from components that could otherwise suffer damage due to excessive temperatures. This critical function was instrumental in the evolution of fins as essential components in engine cooling systems, particularly within Internal Combustion Engines. In essence, fins play a pivotal role in optimizing heat transfer processes across various applications, ensuring efficient cooling and operation of systems subjected to thermal stresses.

2. Literature survey

The literature reviewed encompasses various studies on engine cylinder fins conducted using different software tools for design and analysis, primarily SOLIDWORKS, CATIA V5, and PRO E, with thermal analysis performed using ANSYS software. Sujan Shrestha et al. Designed engine cylinder fins using SOLIDWORKS, analyzed heat transfer and temperature distribution with ANSYS R19.2. Noted low heat transfer rate for gray

cast iron fins, with a 9% deviation between theoretical and simulated values [1]. Ranga Reddy Muddasani et al. Modeled engine cylinders with various fin geometries using CATIA V5, analyzed temperature distribution and heat flux with ANSYS Workbench. Found aluminum 6061 circular fins provided superior heat transfer rates and reduced weight compared to rectangular fins [2]. Ruchir Parikh et al. Conducted ANSYS analysis on engine fins with different shapes, highlighting serrated strip fins for effective temperature reduction compared to rectangular and circular fins [3]. Ravindra Mohan et al. Used CATIA V5 to design IC engine cylinders, analyzed thermal characteristics using ANSYS, emphasizing improved thermal performance of proposed models [4]. A. Harinath et al. Designed engine cylinders with aerodynamic fins using UNIGRAPHIC software, analyzed temperature distribution and heat flux with ANSYS V15.0, highlighting aluminum alloy's high thermal conductivity benefits [5]. S. Mankayam et al. Employed SOLIDWORKS to design engine cylinders with various fin shapes and materials, conducted thermal analysis with ANSYS, identifying aluminum alloy AL200 as optimal for thermal behavior [6]. Jagdeesh Saini Designed engine fins with holes using CREO 3.0, analyzed heat flux and temperature distribution with ANSYS 15.0, noting increased heat distribution with larger hole sizes [7]. Obula Reddy et al. Used GAMBIT software to design engine cylinder blocks with varying materials, analyzed heat and thermal characteristics with ANSYS 15.0, highlighting magnesium and gray cast iron for superior heat transfer rates [8]. Divyank Dubey et al. Modeled engine cylinder blocks with varying fin thicknesses and materials using SOLIDWORKS, analyzed heat transfer and temperature distributions using ANSYS Workbench, noting maximum heat transfer rates with 75mm slotted fins [9]. D. Madhavi et al. Designed engine cylinders with fins in SOLIDWORKS, analyzed heat flux and temperature for different fin materials using ANSYS, recommending aluminum alloy for superior heat dissipation [10]. Raviulla, Ashish Muchrikar Designed engine cylinder fins with different geometries using SOLIDWORKS, analyzed temperature and heat flux distributions with ANSYS, highlighting triangular fins for improved heat transfer efficiency [11]. A. Ramesh Kumar, S. Nandha Kumar Designed engine cylinders with extended fins using SOLIDWORKS, evaluated temperature distribution and heat flux using ANSYS, showing enhanced heat transfer with fin extensions [12]. A. Satish Kumar, MD Karthir Kaman, S. Ponsankar Used SOLIDWORKS to design engine cylinders with varied geometries and materials, analyzed temperature distribution and heat flux with ANSYS, recommending aluminum alloy AL2014 for superior thermal conductivity [13]. G. Selvaraj, N. Alagirisamy, M. S. Santosh Modeled engine cylinder fins with different geometries using SOLIDWORKS, analyzed temperature and pressure distributions with ANSYS, noting circular fins' superior heat transfer capabilities [14]. Pulkit Sagar, Punnet Teotia, H.C. Thakur, Akash Deep Designed engine cylinders with aluminum alloy 6061 fins and varying surface roughness using SOLIDWORKS, analyzed thermal characteristics with ANSYS R15.0, noting increased heat flux with surface roughness [15]. K. Ashok Reddy, T.V. Seshi Reddy, S. Satpagiri Designed engine cylinders with different geometries using SOLIDWORKS, evaluated temperature distribution and heat flux with ANSYS, recommending circular fins for improved efficiency despite a 10% increase in mass [16]. Deepak Gupta, Wankhade S.R. Designed engine cylinder fins with varied geometries using PRO E, analyzed heat transfer rate and nodal temperatures using ANSYS, highlighting aluminum alloy 6063 for superior heat transfer despite increased weight [17]. B.N. Niroop Kumar Gowd, Ramatulasi Used PRO ENGINEER to design engine cylinders with varied geometries and materials, evaluated nodal temperature and heat flux with ANSYS, suggesting modifications in fin shape to optimize heat transfer [18]. N. Phani Raja Rao, T. Vishnu Vardhan Designed engine cylinder fins using PRO E, analyzed temperature distribution using ANSYS, highlighting improved heat transfer rates with thinner and circular-

shaped fins [19]. P. Sai Chaitanya, B. Sunnela Ram, K. Vijaya Kumar Modeled circular and rectangular fins using PRO-E, analyzed heat transfer rate and nodal temperature with ANSYS, showing aluminum alloy 6061 circular fins as optimal for heat transfer efficiency [20]. These studies collectively emphasize the importance of fin design and material selection in optimizing heat transfer efficiency in engine cylinders, utilizing advanced software tools for precise analysis and performance enhancement.

3. DESIGNING OF IC ENGINE CYLINDER FIN

The addition of fins to engine cylinders enhances heat transfer by promoting convection. In thermal analysis, understanding heat dissipation through these fins and assessing stress from temperature and pressure are crucial. Engine chambers experience simultaneous temperature and pressure, necessitating study of their combined effects on engine deformations and stresses.

Thermal conductivity is a critical material property influencing heat dissipation from internal surfaces to external environments. This study focuses on simulating IC engine cylinders with various materials to analyze thermal and structural stress distributions, alongside heat flux distributions. The goal is to gain a comprehensive understanding of IC engine behavior, aiding in the optimization of design for enhanced performance and durability.

Material Properties

Material	Tensile Strength (Mpa)	Young's modulus (Gpa)	Density (kg/m3)	Specific Heat (j/kgk)	Thermal conductivity (W/mk)
Mg alloy	230	45	1810	1050	72
Aluminum Alloy 6061	310	73	2700	1256	167
Grey Cast Iron	255	54	7200	45	46
Titanium Alloy	930	120	4620	553	21.9

Dimensions of finned I.C Engine

PARAMETER	DATA
Length of cylinder	74mm
No of fins	7 (Square fins of 120*120 mm)
Width of fin	2 – 3 mm
Total Surface area of fins	$146.62 * 10^3 \text{ mm}^2$
Pitch of fins	10mm

Fig: 3.1 Modelling of geometry

Fig:3.2 Boundary conditions of geometry

4. Results and discussions

TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION

1. Aluminum 6061 alloy

2. Magnesium alloy

3. Gray Cast Iron Alloy

4. Titanium alloy

TOTAL HEAT FLUX DISTRIBUTION

1. Aluminum 6061 alloy

2. Magnesium alloy

3. Gray cast iron alloy

4. Titanium alloy

Importing of thermal solutions to static structural section

Applying of pressure and remote displacement

TOTAL DEFORMATION

1. Aluminum 6061 alloy

2. Magnesium alloy

3. Gray cast iron alloy

4. Titanium alloy

EQUIVALENT STRESS

1. Aluminum 6061 alloy

2. Magnesium alloy

3. Gray cast iron alloy

4. Titanium alloy

c. EQUIVALENT STRAIN

1. Aluminum 6061 alloy

2. Magnesium alloy

3. Gray cast iron alloy

4. Titanium alloy

Comparison of Results:

Material	Temp distribution (c) (min)	Total heat flux (w/m ²) (max)	Total heat flux (w/m ²) (min)	Total deformation (m) (max)	Total deformation (m) (min)	Equivalent Stress (pa) (max)	Equivalent stress (pa) (min)	Equivalent strain (max)	Equivalent strain (min)
Al Alloy 6061	578.31	2.5360e5	372.90	1.0807e-3	3.315e-4	2.1044e7	2343.1	3.0543e-4	1.1733e-7
Magnesium	551.66	2.4493e5	382.86	1.1953e-3	3.7075e-4	3.2546e7	3560.6	7.2325e-4	2.3182e-7
Grey cast iron	527.18	2.3694e5	409.14	4.957e-4	1.5459e-4	4.9433e7	6184.8	4.4939e-4	2.1027e-7
titanium	462.82	2.1573e5	536.33	4.227e-4	1.2947e-4	6.7807e7	7637.6	7.0637e-4	2.1655e-7

Graph1: Material vs Temperature distribution

Graph2: Material vs Heat flux distribution

Graph 3: Graph2: Material vs Maximum deformation

Graph4: Material vs Maximum equivalent stress

Graph5: Material vs Maximum equivalent strain

CONCLUSION

- In present work, a cylinder fin body is modeled and transient thermal and static structural analysis is done by using CATIA V5 and ANSYS WORKBENCH. These fins are used for air cooling systems for two wheelers. In present study, Aluminum alloy 6061, magnesium alloy, gray cast iron and titanium alloy are used and compared with each other alloys.
- The materials are considered in the study. By changing the material of the fin results in increasing the heat transfer rate and for less deformation and stresses.
- Heat transfer rate in the aluminum 6061 alloy is higher compared to the magnesium and the other alloys.
- Equivalent Stresses developed in the engine are high in titanium alloy and low in the aluminum 6061 alloy. Equivalent strain in the magnesium alloy is high and less in the aluminum 6061 alloy.

- The results shows, by using the fin with material Aluminum Alloy 6061 has better heat transfer rate and also has a better structural characteristics.

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